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Research Article

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ABSTRACT

The main objective of this study provides test of APT for Tehran stock market and also attempt to find the relevant factors that price the stock returns over time. Tests conducted using the principal component analysis and canonical correlation model showed that at least one to three factors can explain the cross-section of expected returns in this market. In full sample test, the evidence identifies 22 factors in sample and only 13 are priced. Again, in second sub period, there are 24 common factors from the smallest to largest samples and only 15 are priced. This study discovers that the sources of systematic risk are dissimilar due to the different periods in TSE. In full period the sources of risk are export of crude oil and interest rate proxy. In second sub periods money supply (M2), money supply (M1), consumer price index and GDP are sources of risk. So, the sources of systematic risks in TSE are dissimilar and not quantified. The important macroeconomic variables could be affected by stock returns changes during times. Therefore, it is hard to identify exactly which is the source of risk in TSE.

Keywords: Principal component Factor analysis, time variability, Canonical Correlation and Arbitrage Pricing theory.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The Capital Asset Pricing Theory (CAPM) commences with an examination of how investors make efficient portfolios and the theory has its foundation in mean variance analysis, whereas, the APT issues from a completely different aspect. It does not ask which portfolios are efficient. Instead, it starts by assuming that each equity return depends partly on pervasive factors and partly on noise (Brealey et al., 2006). The CAPM has been more extensively employed in industry and extremely tested than the APT. Possibly, this is due to its relative simplicity rather than any apparent advantage in explaining expected security returns. The CAPM theory itself stated the single factor is market risk or covariance risk. On the contrary, the APT does not indicate the number of factors, also does not tell us what the factors are, but its interior reason that price-relevant factors are establishing the return which is a reasonable logic of this theory. This causes its application elegant but, less simple as well as demanding more complex methodology for its implementation.

Nevertheless, both the Capital Asset Pricing Model (CAPM) and the Arbitrage Pricing theory (APT) treat the systematic risk of securities as invariant in the end, also, they expose theoretical and empirical evidence that the rate of return of a security changes over time. Furthermore, theoretical investigations relate variability in expected rate of return to intertemporal varieties in macroeconomic variables. Among the benefits of employing the APT while contrasted to other similar methods such as the Capital Asset Pricing Model, the Gordon Valuation model etc., it gives a better entire account of return. Since APT is a general model and employ K-factor model in the return generating process, Elton et al. (1995) state that the APT gives a better justification for return than any other market proxies.

Therefore, this study attempts to test the intertemporal variability of APT in a volatile economy. The main objective of this study provides test of APT for Tehran stock market, a volatile stock market, and also attempt to find the relevant factors that price the stock returns over time.

This paper is organized as follows. Next section summarizes the evidence on APT theories; third section explains the method and research designs; fourth section includes discussion on findings and fifth section explains the conclusion.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

Many studies on APT are in developed markets after the seminal Chen et al., (1985) paper. Elton et al. (1995) employed the MVM APT model to scrutinize the performance of bond funds. To study which of the macro variables that they have been selected were concerned to the bond returns they employed canonical correlation. To test the APT limitations on the macro variables on four alternative models they after that employed iterated non-linear seemingly unrelated regressions. They noted that in favor of models that contained the variables the models that did not include the macroeconomic variables were rejected at the five percent level.

Cheng (1995) employed an option to the method of Chen et al.(1985) to examine connection between security prices and macroeconomic factors in the APT. He accomplished factor analysis on both asset returns and a set of U.K. macroeconomic variables and contrasted the outcome employing canonical correlation. He noted two significant factors for security returns and three significant factors for the economic indicators. The first pair of canonical varieties was attained from the factor scores of the first factor of security returns and the returns of the first factor of economic indicators. There was strong canonical correlation here (canonical correlation value of 0.7243) representing the first economic factor including of market indices was significant in describing security returns. The second pair of canonical varieties consisted of the factor scores of the second factor of security returns and factor scores of the second and third returns on the economic indicators. He noted that even though the second pair of canonical varieties was statistically significant, their correlation was very weak. These economic indices contained interest rate, money supply, gross redemption yield on gilts, unemployment for second factor, and industrial production, GDP and consumer expenditure on durable goods for the third factor. Consequently, the findings in that research identify the existence of one dominate factor that is pricing securities in the APT sense in the UK, and that is the return on the market, in spite of that pricing of securities may be systematically affected by a number of economic forces.

Günsel and Çukur (2007) examined the performance of the Arbitrage Pricing Theory (APT) again in the latest period in London Stock Exchange for the period of 1980-1993 as monthly. The research extended seven pre-specified macroeconomic variables. The expression structure of interest rate, the exchange rate, the risk premium, the money supply and unanticipated inflation were like those resulting in Chen et al. (1986). The research expanded the approach of Chen et al. by adding up industry precise variables, like sectoral dividend yield and sectoral unexpected production. Nonetheless, the consequences show that macroeconomic factors have a significant effect in the UK stock exchange market and each factor may well influence different industry in different way. That is to say, macroeconomic factor may influence one industry positively, but may influence the other industry negatively. There might be distinction among dividend yields for each industry. Thus, sectoral dividend yield employed for every industry is a good alternative for industrial profitability. It is intricate to clarify the negative sign. This may be because of expectations, or the derivation of unexpected dividend yield. Lagged effect is present for some industries which oppose to efficient market hypothesis. As there is no significant relationship between unexpected inflation and sectoral return, test outcome also maintain the efficient market hypothesis for the unexpected inflation case. That is since market predicts it and includes into the stock prices before announcement. As argued before, effective exchange rate is a significant factor for tradable industries.

Gatter and Priestley (1997) demonstrated that statements about whether the factor structure was strict or estimated do matter in determining the significant macroeconomic factors. Employing U.K. data, they explained that none of the factors were priced when returns were presumed to have a strict factor structure. Nevertheless, if an approximate factor where idiosyncratic returns were permitted to be simultaneously correlated across securities were presumed, six factors were priced, viz unexpected inflation, industrial production, the money supply, default risk, the exchange rate and excess returns on the market portfolio.

Antoniou et al. (1998), giving a total of 164 observations, employed data from the period January 1980 to August 1993. They employed returns on 138 individual securities chosen randomly from those securities for which data exist. Then, these securities were randomly divided into two samples: the first sample was the estimation sample and the second sample was a validation sample to test the scheme that the similar factors were priced and achieved in both samples the identical prices of risk. They employed excess returns in every sample and calculated as the security return minus the one month United Kingdom Treasury Bill Rate on sixty- nine individual securities. For excess returns on the market they also contained an equation. Since the market portfolio was treated as endogenous this gave them a system of seventy equations to be estimated by NL3SLS. The macroeconomic factors employed were unexpected inflation and changes in expected inflation, unexpected shocks to retail sales, unexpected shocks to commodity prices, unexpected shocks to industrial production, unexpected shocks to the term structure, unexpected shocks to default risk, unexpected shocks to the exchange rate, unexpected shocks to the money supply and the market portfolio. They found that in the sense that three factors regarding the money supply, for two sub samples of assets, it was likely to turn up at a single return generating procedure inflation and excess returns on the stock market were priced and took the same prices of risk in both samples.

Nasreen (2001) investigates the validity of Capital Asset Pricing Model (CAPM) and Arbitrage pricing theory (APT) and its factor models in describing pricing of assets across time. For different time periods three sub-sets of sample are formed on the foundation that throughout each sub-set of samples the UK economy practiced different economic conditions (1980-1997). This research employed two-stage regression method for estimating. According to Chen et al. (1986) the study demonstrated that for the three subsets of time-periods, which was made from the sample, the value weighted market return has significant descriptive power on pricing for all three-time periods (testing CAPM). Nevertheless, its descriptive power on pricing reduces after addition of the unexpected economic factors (i.e. testing APT). The study also recognized the fundamental methodology difficulty of testing standard CAPM and its factor models across time: different economic factors capture the variation in average returns for different time periods. The sub-sets of samples tighten up with the economic cycles; the consequences thus proposed that as the riskiness of the economy alters over time, the factors at work alter. In other words, the risk premia of factors alter over time in relation to different economic situation. These consequences challenged the aptness of the CAPM and its factor models to elucidate pricing of securities across time and particularly designate that the standard methodology perhaps strained when applied across time.

Groenewold and Fraser (1997) employed data from December 1979 to April 1994 gained from Australian Stock Exchange. They employed the two-stage regression process to recognize the significant factors. They employed FIML technique to estimate the APT equation employing two factors recognized from the regression above. They discovered that the set of priced in Australia overlaps significantly with those in other countries. Their consequences pointed out that short-term interest rate, the inflation rate and money growth rate were priced. They also found that both versions of the APT obviously had better within-sample descriptive power than the CAPM and contrasted the performance of the macro-factor APT model to the artificial factor APT version and the CAPM, but that all models performed inadequately out of samples.

Azeez and Yonezawa (2006) performed the research of APT on Japanese stock market. This research has studied the empirical evidence of the pricing of macroeconomic factors in the Japanese stock market during the bubble economy. For this reason, they used the APT which first enabled them to recognize those macroeconomic factors that were a basis of systematic risk, and second, to contrast the priced factors of the bubble period with the priced factors of pre-and post-bubble periods. They observed that the pricing limitations the APT places on an unrestricted linear factor model, in the preceding section, could not be rejected. On all the assessments this looks to offer the support for the APT as an asset pricing model. In other words, their null hypothesis that expected returns are concluded by the APT with risk factors gained employing present value model of stock price is established. They have come to the conclusion that in each of the sample period four various kinds of risk factors have significant influence on expected returns. They included exchange rate, money supply, inflation, and industrial production. The magnitudes of risk premiums in absolute values improved during the bubble and post-bubble periods in comparison to pre-bubble period, though the number of priced factors and the signs of risk premiums were about stable across each period. In the meantime, in the bubble period the variances of macroeconomic factors were not increased. During the bubble period the higher risk premiums should be because of the increase of bubble crash risk. For the meantime regarding putting restriction on APT, the research employed Fama and Macbeth two-stage regression methodology. Identifying the APT in this mode has several specific advantages over the two-step methodology. In terms of econometric matters, the non-linear apparently unrelated regression methodology presents joint estimation of the parameters of the APT and therefore eliminates the errors invariables problem. An additional benefit of this condition is that the vital APT across equation limitations that the prices of risk are equal for all assets can be directly forced and tested.

Not many factor analytic empirical tests of the APT in less developed markets have been reported in the serious journals. Van Rensburg (1996) accomplished many researches on the APT in the thinly traded Johannesburg Stock Exchange in South Africa. He examined the appropriateness of the MVM version of the APT during eight years and he knew that short-term interest rate, the Dow Jones Industrial Index, the term structure of interest rates and the residual market factor of Burmeister and Wall (1986) had significant priced risk premia. Nevertheless, as probable candidates, the variety of macro variables tested was not widespread such as the default premia in Chen et al. (1986) were not tested on account of unavailability of quality data. Van Rensburg (2000) examined again the Chen et al. (1986) pre-specified variable procedure to priced APT identification on the Johannesburg Stock Exchange (JSE). In this investigation, he employed an independent and more current share sample than that used by Van Rensburg (1996). He used the Vector Autoregressive Regression (VAR) methodology; unanticipated activities in the factors were extracted accounting for the analytical power of the other sequences in the structure of investor anticipations. This research demonstrated that a two indices model, namely employing returns on the all-Gold, and Industrial Indices as explanatory variables considers the effect of the other pre-specified macroeconomic variables on equity returns.

3.0 METHODOLOGY AND DATA ANALYSIS

The Tehran Stock Exchange (TSE) was founded in February 1967 and began its first year of activity with only five companies. As of April 2009, there are 421 companies listed on the TSE with a total market capitalization of US\$52,452.5 million. (TSE yearly bulletin, 2009). In the Middle East countries, TSE is ranked 17th based on market capitalization as a percent of GDP.

The analysis period in this study, covers 17 years from 20th March 1991 to 19th March in 2008. This is so far the most comprehensive test of APT in this market. The analysis is divided into two periods, full sample 1991-2008 and sub-period sample 1999-2008, respectively. The stocks chosen in this research are taken randomly from Main Board of Tehran Stock Exchange Market (TSE). Nevertheless, there are 80 stocks chosen, 20 stocks were removed because of the incomplete information. A total of 60 stocks were selected in first sub period. Since the number of securities increased for the period beyond 1998, 160 stocks were chosen for the second sub-period.

The main objective of this study is to test APT in the Tehran Stock Exchange (TSE) using unidentified factors and macroeconomic variables. This is done first by identifying the macro APT-relevant factors that affect security returns, and after which extending the factor matrix to include factor(s) relevant to less developed economies.

In the above section, it was shown that different methodologies and research designs have been used to test APT in different markets. This study tests the APT using factor analysis with principal component analysis and Canonical Correlation Analysis (CCA). The test is carried out before and after a financial crisis that destabilized the economy to ascertain the impact of the structural changes in the economy and the securities market as a consequence of the crises.

The stock price data for this study are the monthly returns on stocks on the main board of the TSE. The returns are calculated using month-end prices, i.e., $R_{it} = (P_t - P_{t-1}) / P_{t-1}$, where R_{it} is the return per period t for the period being computed, P_t is the price of the stock at the end of the period t , and P_{t-1} is the price of the stock at the end of the period $t-1$. The returns are adjusted for dividends, bonus issues, rights issues and stock splits.

Based on the studies by Chen et al. (1986), Clare and Priestley (1998) and Mohseni (2007), a variety of macroeconomic and financial factors and a proxy for the market were selected, inclusive those factors that are peculiar to TSE. Variables selected were Consumer Price Index (CPI), Trade Balance, Money Supply (M_1 , M_2), Exchange Rate (Rial / US\$), Central Bank Reserve, Volume of Stock Transaction of TSE, Tehran Price Index (TEPIX), Oil Price, Production of Crude Oil, Export of Crude Oil, Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and Interest rate proxy (ROE of banks). Monthly data was used and all the economic variables are measured by rate of change rather than absolute values.

The procedure to test the APT is as follows: First, factor analysis with Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was applied to determine the individual securities and portfolios factor loadings estimate to explain the cross-sectional variation of individual and portfolios estimated returns. Second, cross-sectional regressions were run to determine the number of priced factors to measure the size and statistical significant of risk premium associated with the estimated factors from the common factors extracted in the first stage. This procedure repeated for individual securities and different size of portfolios for Full period and two sub-periods separately. The reasons why stocks are grouped into portfolios are to eliminate diversifiable risk and to reduce the errors-in-variables problem in the second stage cross-sectional regression; this is an established procedure. This study stocks ordered by size and also, employing different size of portfolios increase the reliability of the results.

In the first stage, the principal component factor analysis procedure will describe the return in the following way:

$$R_{it} = b_{i1}PC_1 + b_{i2}PC_2 + b_{i3}PC_3 + \dots + b_{ik}PC_k \quad (1)$$

Where, R_{it} is individual securities or portfolios return; b_{ik} is known as factor loadings, which can be used to represent the sensitivity of the security against the asset i 's returns to the movements in the common factors; PC_k is the principal component scores of asset i . To test general hypothesis in this study is to identify that b 's are priced in the arbitrage pricing relationship. Thus, in this study, the b 's will be used to test the pricing of risky factors. This traditional test using the APT is usually undertaken by implementing a cross-sectional regression procedure used in Black et al. (1972) and Fama and MacBeth (1973) methodology in the following way:

$$E(R_{it}) = \lambda_0 + \sum_{k=1}^k \lambda_k b_{ik} \quad (2)$$

If APT is valid, the same number of priced factors must be statistically significant. This study utilized the p - values to determine the significance of the individual risk premia and vector of risk premia respectively.

4.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

All the tests are conducted for 60 individual securities for the full period. Since the number of securities increased in the TSE during recent years, we used 160 securities in second sub-period.

4.1 Descriptive Statistics of Security Returns

Table 4.1a summarized the descriptive statistics for full period, second sub period. Sixty Individual securities are considered for full periods. Also, for achieving precise results the descriptive analyses of 160 Individual securities are reported in this table. According to this table all of stock returns have positive mean excess returns. All the variables are more volatile in second sub period as regards to standard deviation of stock returns. However, Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilks tests show that all of stocks returns are normally distributed.

Table 4.1a: Summary of Descriptive Statistics - Security Returns

	Full Period 60 IS	Second Sub Period 160IS
Mean	3.27	5.54
Standard Deviation	6.71	21.57
Kolmogorov-Smirnov	.000*	.000*
Shapiro-Wilk	.000*	.000*

Note: IS: Individual Securities.

Full Period: 1991-2008.

Second Sub Period: 1999-2008.

*: Normality significant at 1 percent level.

4.2 Descriptive Statistics of Macroeconomic Variables

In this section discussions of the descriptive statistics of macroeconomic variables are repeated. Table 4.1b summarized the descriptive test for the full period, sub period one and sub period two respectively. Comparing the two sub periods, the outcome represented that the average rate of most of the macroeconomic variables were higher after financial crisis (Second Sub Period). It is also perceived that the standard deviation for most of the macroeconomic variables were higher in second sub period too. This study finds that most of macroeconomic variables were more volatile in sub-period two than sub period one. The higher volatile of macroeconomic variables could be due to the effect of 1997 financial crisis and tightening of sanctions in second sub period. As the result shows, for normality test all the macroeconomic variables are also normally distributed.

Table 4.1b: Summary of Descriptive Statistics- Macroeconomic Variables

Macroeconomic Variables	Full Period		Second Sub Period	
	Mean	Std.Dv	Mean	Std.Dv
Consumer Price Index (Index Number)	54.32	38.76	82.8341	29.61
Central Bank Reserve (Billions Rials)	79796.29	133606.17	141822.99	156175.83
Exchange Rate (National Currency per US Dollar)	4049.58	3557.23	6346.61	3350.92

Money Supply(M1) (Billions Rials)	123181.09	115693.86	199733.34	107112.621
Money Supply(M2) (Billions Rials)	161139.35	170637.95	266247.87	170186.149
Crude Oil Production (Index Number)	94.4715	5.1	95.56	5.27413
Trade Balance (Millions Rials)	4554.98	25497.16	9457.70	33709.3
Oil Price (Million Rials)	24243.23	50425.27	44335	61635
Tehran Price Index (TEPIX) (Millions Rials)	4289.28	4213.58	7042.22	3955.12
Volume of Stock Transaction (Millions Rials)	744800.65	2690552.0	1356310.2	3539965.63
Export of Crude Oil (Thousand barrels per day)	2434.4167	227.87073	2352.08	224.34
Interest rate proxy (percent)	1.79	1.99	1.11	1.29
GDP (Billions Rials)	80098.62	56530.197	88618.75	15429.64

4.3 Factor analysis

4.3.1 Full period

Recognition of factors under this method involves forming different samples ranging from a large to small ones. It is sensible to presume as is done in this procedure to speculate that the number of factors will rise with rising number of stocks in a sample since the idiosyncratic factors must rise with difference in the exposure to factors. This arises from the factor-specificity of corporate activities.

Employing the full period meant that the number of firms that were frequently traded were few. Therefore, the first test is done with 60 firms. The data matrix for this test used 204 x60 items formed by 60 securities. Each vector has components corresponding to the 204 monthly observations. The results of principal component analysis are represented in Table 5.2. The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin test (KMO) value is 0.63 and Bartlett's test of sphericity is significant at 100 percent acceptance level indicating that the principal component factor analysis is appropriate for this data set.

The analysis identified 22 factors based on the identification criterion that eigenvalue for factor selection must exceed 1. We predicted the contribution made by every factor. Thoroughly, the twenty- two components explained about 71 percent of the variance in returns. It emerges that this capital market pricing is potentially affected by at least fourteen factors (employing a simple majority rule) and 22 factors if we imposed 71 percent expiation. This finding is compatible with the other finding of market such as U.K. study employing 80 stocks identified 20 factors that elucidated a majority of the returns variance in that market. Based on Kryzanowski and To's (1983), the factor structure differ minimally through the samples. Consequently, this outcome is consistent with Kryzanowski and To (1983) discovering that as the number of observation raise, the relative significance of the first factor in the terms of the accounting for the total variances appears to rise. In addition, the first factor has perfect generalizability that disappears quickly from the second factors onwards (Kryzanowski and To, 1983).

Finally, we proceed to test the model. The cross-section regression of the means stock market for the 17-year period was performed against the 22 factor loadings. The results indicated that the 9 factors are jointly

significant as evidence by F-value of 89.41, which is well above the acceptance level of 0.000 (see Table 4.2, column 1 and 2). On an individual factor basis, 9 factors were found to significantly affect the prices: the t- values ranged from 11.8 to 0.24, all above the critical value for five percent level of significant for the sample. The financial and economical dummy variables were not significant at 1, 5 or 10 percent level of significant. The adjusted R- squared value was high at 0.93.

Some preliminary studies may be made from the results of analysis for the full period of 17 years from 1991-2008. First, the number of factors extracted based on Kaiser Criterion increases as the sample enhance. This is in proportion to the finding in developed markets. The factors describe about 50 to 81 percent of the variance in returns. Second, the F-test presents that the factors extracted were jointly significant at five percent level in all of the cases. Third, the t-tests show that up to two factors significantly were priced, with the bulk of the cases two. Forth, financial and economical dummy variables are significant at 5 and 10 percent level in almost all of the cases, except in sixty individual securities and fifteen portfolios. It means that the financial and economic sanctions are affecting the volatility of stocks returns. Fifth, the coefficients' sign of the dummy variables are negative for all the cases. It shows the negative reaction of stock return to the sanctions. Finally, the adjusted R-squared values were high with the values between 0.93 up to 0.99. Therefore, the findings are reliable.

Table 4.2:Factor analysis and Cross-Sectional Regression of average returns against factor scores coefficients

	60 Individual Securities		160 Individual Securities
Total Variance Explained	71%	Total Variance Explained	86%
No. of Common Factors	22	No. of Common Factors	24
No. of the Priced Factors	9	No. of the Priced Factors	13
λ_1	2.25*** (5.63)	λ_1	2.54*** (16.01)
λ_2	1.75** (3.1)	λ_2	0.48*** (2.92)
λ_3	1.84*** (11.8)	λ_3	0.83*** (4.9)
λ_4	2.19*** (3.9)	λ_4	1.06*** (7.31)
λ_5	1.87*** (5.11)	λ_5	0.86*** (6.69)
λ_6	1.39*** (5.11)	λ_6	0.54** (2.36)
λ_7	1.06*** (7.88)	λ_7	0.52*** (3.28)
λ_8	0.42** (2.39)	λ_8	0.27** (2.07)
λ_9	0.36*** (2.6)	λ_9	0.48*** (3.79)
		λ_{10}	0.64*** (4.85)
		λ_{11}	0.32** (2.60)
		λ_{12}	0.22* (1.68)
		λ_{13}	0.3** (2.09)
F	89.41	F	18.52
Sig.F	0.00***	Sig.F	0.00***
KMO	0.63	KMO	0.63
Adj-R Square	0.93	Adj-R Square	0.88

Note: N=No. of Factors from factor analysis. t- Values in bracket.

Common factors are factors obtained in factor analysis that have eigen value greater than 1, Price factors are factors that are significant in the regression

*Significant at 10% level. ** Significant at 5% level. *** Significant at 1% level. Only priced factors at 1%, 5% and 10% significant level are shown.

4.3.2 Second Sub- period (1999-2008)

For this second period, analysis was conducted in the same manner as above for various sample size. As the number of securities increased in this sub period, so for getting precise results, 160 securities employed. Moreover evaluating this sub-period on its own, comparison can also be made with the full 17-year and also the first 10- year sub-period.

For this sample size, principal component analysis extracted 24 factors based on the Kaiser Criterion. According to Table 4.2, column 3 and 4, the 24 factors explain 86 percent of the total variance in returns. In the cross-sectional regression, thirteen factors were priced at the 1 and 5 percent level of significance. The factors were jointly significant as indicated by the F-value. The adjusted R-square was 0.88. None of the financial and economical dummy variables were significant at one, five and ten percent. These results are better than those of the full 17-year period and the first sub period.

For this sub- period, the set of factors extracted based on the Kaiser Criterion increased in sample size. Therefore, this trend observed for previous sub-period and the whole 17-year period is maintained. The numbers of factors extracted from principal components show to be approximately the higher for both first sub-period and 17- year period. The factors explain over 61-86 percent of the variance in returns as in the first sub-period and 17-year period. In one of the sample size financial and economic sanctions is significant. The results show the negative reaction of stock market returns to the sanctions. However, in terms of cross-sectional explanatory power, this latter sub-period present worst outcome compared to the earlier period as seen via the adjusted R-squared values. This explanatory power is also comparable to that employing the 17-year period. Table 4.2, column 3 and 4, demonstrates the summary of finding in the second sub period.

4.3.3 Principal Component Factor Analysis: A Discussion

The principal component factor analysis indicated in this session is for recognizing the structure of the Tehran Stock Exchange. There is strong evidence in the literature for applying principal component factor analysis of APT in several markets. In agreement with the literature, the number of common factors that the researcher is able to extract by using principal component factor analysis increases linearly with the sample size increase. The number of common factors increases from 22 to 24 as the sample size is increased from 60 to 160 individual securities. That is, factor specificity in the case of smaller sample means that only about 22 factors are relevant for inter-temporal pricing of the securities in smaller samples (see Table 4.2).

Therefore, even in larger sample the numbers of factors that really have a significant effect are only little more in number despite the eigenvalue of 1.00 is exceeded by a large number of factors. This finding is in line with previous studies like Roll and Ross (1980), Kryzanowski and To (1983), Dhrymes et al.(1984) and Beenstock and Chan (1986) and Lim and Ariff (2005).

This evidence of increase in number of factors with sample size is not inconsonant with the prediction of APT, which does not predict the actual number of relevant factors. Nevertheless, this is atypical and weakness of the factor analytic approach. The numbers of common factors are perceptible to number of the sample.

Cross-sectional two -stage OLS regression was applied to test the general objective of this study. The general objective of this study is to test the applicability of the APT as a theory of asset pricing in Tehran Stock Exchange (TSE) that is active in exact Islamic close economy. According to general objective of this study, the general hypothesis was tested. The general hypothesis implies that: APT is helpful for predicting stock price in TSE that is active in an exact Islamic close economy. The APT equation can only be accepted if at least one of risk premia λ_n is significant.

Nevertheless, two tests were carried out. The first test is related to Risk Premia λ_n . Two types of tests are conducted. One is a t-test on the coefficient of factors and another is a joint F-test on all the factors together. It has been pointed out by Chen (1983) and Dhrymes et al. (1984) that estimation of factor loadings in factoranalysis entails rotation of factors and this means that the number of priced factors is indeterminate. The APT theory can be rejected if none of the factors in cross sectional regression is significant.

However, F test and t- test demonstrate that for all the samples in all periods, at least one of the factors is significant at the one or five percent level. The significant F values of all the samples are 100.00 percent. The evidence points out to at least 9 factors that explain the cross-section of expected returns on the Tehran stock market in the full periods. Results achieved in this study support the hypothesis that at least the risk premia is not significant from zero. These findings are inconsistent with the results of openeconomy with regard to Hughes (1982) for the Canadian stock market returns, Roll and Ross (1980) and Chen (1983) based on United States stock market, that only four factors were present. While the results are compatible with Lim and Ariff (2005), and Azhar and Mohammad Ali (2006) studies for Malaysian stock market. Thus, the null hypothesis of the general objective of this study is rejected (see table 4.2).

4.4 The factor Structure of the Iranian Economy

The purpose of this section is to determine the number of Iranian macroeconomic variables in order to estimate the number and loadings of the factors that represents the Iranian economy. The main categories of thirteen macroeconomic variables considered in the analysis contain an extensive spread of economic procedure and selection of the economy. The set of these variables does not exhaust all possibilities, but it does contain these macroeconomic variables, which are generally considered as the most significant in Iranian economy. Because the general APT model has a one-to-one relationship with the macroeconomic variables, most empirical research such as Chen et al. (1986) suggest that the stock market has a one-to-one correspondence with the macroeconomic variables. Nevertheless, in accordance with Groenwold and Fraser (1997), the theory does not state how many macroeconomic variables are reflected in the stock market. In this study, the principal component analysis is employed to construct and identify the independent macroeconomic variables from thirteen Iranian macroeconomic variables. Therefore, the groups of macroeconomic variables were issued to principal component analysis to determine the number and loading of factor, based on the Asian financial crisis on the two sub periods.

4.4.1 Principal Component Scores of Iranian Economy in the Full period (1991-2008)

The principal component analysis implies the results by the full period and summarized in Table 4.3. According to the principal component analysis results, this section implies that there are four main factors underlying the Iranian economy. The Kaiser Criterion is 0.80 for the four factors. The components extracted explain 69.5 percent of the variance in the full period.

The first factor in the full period includes the money supply (M2) with the highest factor loading (0.980), the money supply (M1), central bank reserves, trade balance, exchange rate and oil price with the factor loadings 0.968, 0.955, 0.929, 0.855 and 0.527, respectively. However, the second factor contain the consumer price index with the highest factor loading (0.835), GDP with the factor loading (0.649) and crude oil production with the factor loading (0.600). The third factor consists of TEPIX with the highest factor loading (0.845) and volume of stock transaction with the factor loading (0.786). The fourth factor includes the export of the crude oil with the factor loading (0.823) and interest rate proxy with the factor loading (0.491). The explanation and implications are discuss in section 4.4.3 later.

Table 4.3: Results of Principal Component Analysis of Macroeconomic Variables: Total Variance Explained- Full Period

Factor	Macroeconomic Variables	Factor loading
Factor 1	Money supply(M2)	0.980
	Money supply(M1)	0.968
	Central bank reserves	0.955
	Trade balance	0.929
	Exchange rate	0.855
	Oil price	0.527
Factor2	Consumer price index	0.835
	GDP	0.649
	Crude Oil Production	0.600
Factor3	TEPIX	0.845
	Volume of Stock Transaction	0.786
Factor 4	Export of crude oil	0.823
	Interest Rate Proxy	0.491

4.4.2 Principal Component Scores of Iranian Economy in the Second Sub- period (1999-2008)

As shown in Table 4.4, the results by the first year sub-period are summarized. According to the results, there are four major factors underlying the Iranian economy after financial crisis in sub-period two. The Kaiser criterion in this sample is 0.81. The four principal components explained 81 percent of the variance. The first factor encompasses trade balance with the highest factor loading (0.970), central bank reserves, volume of stock transaction, exchange rate and TEPIX are the rest factor with factor loadings 0.956, 0.906, 0.855 and 0.581 respectively. The second factor consists of money supply (M2) with highest factor loading (0.958), the money supply (M1) with the factor loading (0.955), consumer price index (0.945) and GDP (0.837). The third factor includes oil price, export of the crude oil and

crude oil production with factor loadings 0.783, 0.725 and 0.684. Finally, the fourth factor is interest rate proxy with the factor loading (0.990). The explanation and implications are discuss in section 4.4.3 later.

Table 4.4: Results of Principal Component Analysis of Macroeconomic Variables: Total Variance Explained- Second Sub Period

Factor	Macroeconomic Variables	Factor loading
Factor 1	Trade Balance	0.970
	Central bank reserves	0.956
	Volume of Stock Transaction	0.906
	Exchange rate	0.855
	TEPIX	0.581
Factor2	Money supply(M1)	0.958
	Money supply(M2)	0.955
	Consumer price index	0.945
	GDP	0.837
Factor3	Oil price	0.783
	Crude oil Production	0.725
	Export of crude oil	0.684
Factor4	Interest Rate Proxy	0.990

4.4.3 Principal Component Scores of Iranian Economy Results- A Discussion

The general results from the principal component analysis presents that the thirteen macroeconomic variables were grouped into four factors for full period, five and four factors for first sub- period and second sub- period, respectively. In the full period the first factor explained highest variance of Iranian economy. The most significant factors are money variables in the 17-year full period. The most important factor is money supply (M2) in full period. Changes in the money supply related to unexpected increases in inflation and share price. However, changes in the money supply influence the share price through its result on economy.

Based on the results, the most significant factor in the first sub-period is factor one. Factor one contains the variables concerned to oil. The first factor explains most variance in the Iranian economy. However, oil price is the most essential factor in Iranian economy in this period. As a significant source of global risk, production of crude oil, changes in the crude oil prices and export of crude oil are therefore estimated to significantly influence economic growth in Iran and concern the financial market activity.

Once more, trade balance is most important of first factor in second sub period. Changes in trade balance affect domestic currency and then domestic interest rates. Financial variables are the most important ones that clarify fluctuation in Iranian economy in the second sub period. Financial variables like trade balance, central bank reserves, volume of stock transaction, exchange rate and TEPIX are the most important macroeconomic variables that affect stock market returns in second sub period. The results indicate that Iranians economy affected mostly by financial variable in second sub period. Table 4.5 summarized the factors in the periods.

4.5 Relationship between Stock Market Returns and Macroeconomic Variables

The aim of this section is to analyze the relationship between Iranian stock market returns and macroeconomic variables. In this section, the Canonical Correlation Analysis (CCA) procedure will be employed to identify the economic variables that affect stock market. According to Chen (1995), since the CCA employs a set of dependent variables (principal component scores of stock market returns) and set of independent variables (principal component scores of macroeconomic variables); this thesis can identify the factors of macroeconomic variables that statistically has significant effect to the stock market returns.

Table 4.5: Summarized of the Macroeconomic Variables in the Periods

	Full Period	Second Sub-Period
Factor1	Money supply(M2) Money supply(M1) Central Bank Reserves Trade balance Exchange Rate Oil Price	Trade Balance, Central Bank Reserves, Volume of stock transaction, Exchange Rate TEPIX
Factor2	Consumer Price Index GDP Crude oil production	Money supply(M2), Money supply(M1) Consumer Price Index GDP
Factor3	TEPIX Volume of stock transaction	Oil Price Crude oil production Export of crude oil
Factor4	Export of crude oil Interest rate proxy	Interest rate proxy

The Canonical correlation Analysis is a multivariate statistical method in which we correlate the set of dependent variables with the set of independent variables. When only one dependent variable is available, multiple regressions may be relevant. However, when we believe more than one dependent variable concurrently, separate multiple regressions for each dependent variable will not reflect the joint effects of having multiple dependent variables. Therefore, if this study employs the multiple regressions technique, there would be no occasion to examine the possibility that some combination of dependent variables can be concerned to independent variables (Lambert and Durand, 1975).

4.5.1 Canonical Correlation Analysis in the 17-Year Full Period

The canonical analysis is shown in Table 4.6. Interpretation of the two significant canonical variates from loading will be based on 0.3000 and above of canonical variates. Both the direction of correlation in the loadings matrices and the direction of scales of measurements are considered when interpreting the canonical variates (Tabachnik&Fidell, 1996). Correlation between the stock market returns and macroeconomic variables is shown in Appendix H. As shown in Table 5.13, the first canonical correlation is 0.4162, corresponding to 17.32 percent of the overlapping variance for the first pair of canonical variates. The second canonical correlation is 0.2592 corresponding to 6.72 percent of the overlapping variance between the second pair of canonical variates. The third is 0.2307 corresponding to 5.32 percent of the overlapping variance between the third pair of canonical variates. A fourth canonical correlation is 0.1026 corresponding to 1.05 percent of the overlapping variances between the fourth pair of canonical variates. The first canonical variate is significant at 1 percent level regarding to the F value. Therefore, in sixty individual securities, the first canonical correlation analyses represent a substantial relationship between the first pair of canonical variates; stock market returns and macroeconomic variables. However, second, third and fourth pairs are not significant of the common variance.

The first pair of canonical variates was a high loading on FSMR4 (0.4280) of the principal component scores of the stock market returns and on FMACRO4 (0.5449) and FMACRO3 (0.3926) of the principal component score of the macroeconomic variables. Therefore, the first canonical variables are primarily FSMR4 for the stock market returns and FMACRO3 and FMACRO4 for the macroeconomic variable. The first canonical variate that formed the stock market returns are the most successful linear combination of the security to predict the first canonical variate formed from the macroeconomic variables. The results in Table 5.9 shows that the factor structure of the Iranian economy in the full period, which are the third and fourth factor composed that TEPIX, volume of stock transaction, export of crude oil and interest rate proxy.

The canonical analysis is shown in Table 4.6, sections variance of the principal component scores of stock market returns by their own canonical variate. The values for the first canonical variates are 0.111 for the first set of variables and 0.25 for the second set of variables. This indicates that the first canonical variate pair extracts 11.11 percent of the variance from the principal component scores of stock market returns and 25 percent of the variance

from the principal component scores of macroeconomic variables. The redundancy in a canonical variate is the percent of variance it extracts from its own set of variables multiply the squared canonical correlation for the pair of canonical variates. Thus, the redundancies for the canonical variates are found in Statistical Analysis System Canonical Correlation (SAS CANCORR) in the section labeled variance of the variables explained by the opposite canonical variable as shown Table 5.14. This means that, the first principal components score of the stock market returns variates accounts 1.92 percent of the variance. Nevertheless, the first principal component scores of economic variables were higher variates accounting for 4.33 percent of the variance.

4.5.2 Canonical Correlation Analysis in the Second Sub-Period

It would be interesting to see if the good results for the whole and first sub period are maintained for the second sub-period. For this sub-period, analysis was similarly carried out for various sample size of 160 individual securities, 20, 15, 10 and five portfolios. This period includes the period of the financial crisis. Appendix H shows Correlation between the stock market returns and macroeconomic variables. As shown in Table 5.13, the first canonical correlation is 0.5422 corresponding to 29.4 percent of the overlapping variance for the first pair of canonical variates. The second canonical correlation is 0.3106 corresponding to 9.64 percent of the overlapping variance for the second pair of canonical variates. The third is 0.2947 corresponding to 8.68 percent of the overlapping variance for the third pair of canonical variates. The fourth is 0.1894 corresponding to 3.58 percent of the overlapping variance for the fourth pair of canonical variates.

4.6. Canonical Correlation Analysis

The canonical correlations of the association between the principal component scores of the stock market returns and the principal component score of the macroeconomic variables.

	Canonical Correlation	Squared Canonical Correlation(r_c^2)	Likelihood Ratio	F-Test	Pr>F
Full Period 60 IS					
1	0.4162	0.1732	0.7224	1.81	0.003***
2	0.2592	0.0672	0.8737	1.11	0.33
3	0.2307	0.0532	0.9367	0.92	0.54
4	0.1026	0.0105	0.9894	0.34	0.91
Second Sub Period 160 IS					
1	0.5422	0.2940	0.5614	1.13	0.2577
2	0.3106	0.0964	0.7954	0.63	0.9527
3	0.2947	0.0868	0.8803	0.57	0.9369
4	0.1894	0.0358	0.9641	0.36	0.9603

Note: IS: Individual Securities. *Significant at 10% level. ** Significant at 5% level. *** Significant at 1% level.

The first pair of canonical variates was a high loading on FSMR1 (0.5898) of the principal component scores of the stock market returns and on FMACRO2 (0.8998) of the principal component score of the macroeconomic variable. Thus, the first canonical variables are primarily FSMR1 for the stock market returns and FMACRO2 for the macroeconomic variables. The results in Table 5.11 show that the factor structure of the Iranian economy in the sub-period two is the second factor. Second factor composed of money supply (M2), money supply (M1), consumer price index and GDP.

The canonical analysis is shown in Table 4.6 sections variance of the principal component scores of stock market returns by their own canonical variate. The values for the first canonical variates are 0.0750 for the first set of variables and 0.2500 for the second set of variables. That shows the first canonical variate pair extracts 7.5 percent of the variance from the principal component scores of stock market returns and 25 percent of the variance from the principal component scores of macroeconomic variables. The redundancy in a canonical variate is the percent of

variance it extracts from its own set of variables multiply the squared canonical correlation for the pair of canonical variates. Therefore, the redundancies for the canonical variates are found in Statistical Analysis System Canonical Correlation (SAS CANCORR) in the section labeled variance of the variables explained by the opposite canonical variable as shown in Table 4.7 This means that, the first principal component scores of the stock market returns variates accounts for 2.21 percent of the variance. However, the first principal component scores of economic variables were higher variates accounting for 7.35 percent of the variance.

Table 4.7: Canonical Correlation Analysis in the 17-Year Full period and second sub period

	60 Individual Securities		160 Individual Securities
FSMR	4 FSMR4FF	FFFF	FSMR FSMR14 FFFFFFFF
Shared Variance	11%		Shared Variance 7.5%
Redundancy	1.96%		Redundancy 2.21%
FMACRO	FMACRO4 FMACRO3		FMACRO FMACRO2
Shared Variance	25%		Shared Variance 25%
Redundancy	4.33%		Redundancy 7.35%

Note: FSMR is Principal Component Scores of the Stock Market Returns.

FMACRO is Principal Component Scores of the Macroeconomic Variables.

Shared Variance is Standardized Variance of the Principal Component Scores of Stock Market Returns Explained by their Own Canonical Variate.

Redundancy is Standardized Variance of the Principal Component Scores of Stock Market Returns Explained by the Opposite Canonical Variate.

4.5.3 Canonical Correlation Results-Discussion

In this section, we have examined the relationship between the principal component scores of stock returns that obtained from cross-sectional regression and principal component of macroeconomic variables that extracted from factor structure of Iranian economy. This thesis employed different size of individual securities and portfolios in 17-year full period, first sub-period and second sub period. Different sample size is used to see and compare between the results. In full period the source of systematic risks by using sixty individual securities are FMACRO3 and FMACRO4. In twenty and fifteen portfolios, FMACRO4 is source of volatility in stock returns. Again, in ten portfolios FMACRO2 and FMACRO4 are source of systematic risks. FMACRO4 is source of systematic risks in five portfolios. So, FMACRO4 is same for all of the cases. According to Table 5.12 factor four consist of export of crude oil and interest rate proxy. Therefore, in full period the main sources of systematic risk are export of crude oil and interest rate proxy.

In the first sub period, the sources of systematic risks by using sixty individual securities are FMACRO2 and FMACRO4. In next samples, that is twenty portfolios FMACRO2 and FMACRO5 are sources of systematic risk in TSE. In fifteen and ten portfolios, FMACRO2, FMACRO4 and FMACRO5 are source of risks. CCA is multivariate test and need more than one dependent variable. Since in five portfolios only one dependent variable is extracted, so, we removed five portfolios from this step of data analysis in the first sub period. Therefore, before the financial crisis in first sub period FMACRO2 is repeated for all the samples. So, FMACRO2 could be main source of systematic risk in TSE before the financial crisis. According to Table 5.12, FMACRO2 composed of TEPIX, central bank reserves and GDP.

After the financial crisis, in second sub period, FMACRO2 is source of risk by employing 160 individual securities. FMACRO2 and FMACRO3 are source of volatility of stock returns in twenty, fifteen and ten portfolios. Again, five portfolios are removed from analysis because it could not be consider to CCA as regard to its sole dependent variables. Therefore, after the financial crisis in second sub period FMACRO2 is main source of systematic risk in TSE. According to Table 5.12, FMACRO2 composed of money supply (M2), money supply (M1), consumer price index and GDP.

According to CCA results, it is clear that the macroeconomic variables are affects stock market returns. Therefore, there is a relationship between stock market factor scores and macroeconomic variables. However, the null hypothesis of the first subsidiary hypothesis is rejected. It means that stock market returns could be influenced

by macroeconomic variables. This finding is in agreement with the previous studies such as Clare and Thomas (1994) and Chen (1995).

Table 4.8 summarized the risk factor in every period. As show in this table, the sources of systematic risk are dissimilar due to the different periods in TSE. In full period the sources of risk are export of crude oil and interest rate proxy. In first sub period, TEPIX, central bank reserves and GDP are sources of risk. In second sub periods money supply (M2), money supply (M1), consumer price index and GDP are sources of risk. So, the sources of systematic risks in TSE are dissimilar and not quantified. The important macroeconomic variables that could be affected by stock returns changes over times. Therefore, it is hard to identify exactly which is the source of risk in TSE. Which macroeconomic variables are most important in Iran? These findings also suggest that different strategies are required to invest successfully in Iran because the risk factors changes over time.

Table 4.8: Risk Factors in Full Period and Two Sub Periods

Full Period	Second Sub Period
Export of crude oil	Money supply (M2)
Interest rate proxy	Money supply (M1)
	Consumer Price Index
GDP	

5.0 CONCLUSION

In previous researches on the APT, many researchers used the factor analysis principal component analysis to identify the number of common factors. In this study, three methods are used namely the principal component analysis, cross-sectional two stage Ordinary Least Square (OLS) regression analysis and Canonical Correlation Analysis (CCA). In particular, factor analysis principal component analysis was performed to identify the number of common factors. In accordance with Diacogiannis (1986), the theory behind the APT does not identify returns, as well as the specifying of these factors. Therefore, the security returns-generating model of the APT is an unobservable model and, consequently, the empirical study of the APT model is achieved through exploiting techniques depending only implicitly on the underlying factors.

Correspondingly, it implies that there also exists a recognition problem in the case of the APT, since it does not identify the number and nature of underlying factors, which influence stock market returns. Nevertheless, in full sample test, the evidence identifies 22 factors in sample and only 13 are priced. Again, in second sub period, there are 24 common factors from the smallest to largest samples and only 15 are priced. As suggested by Dharmy et al., (1984), the outcomes of this research show that there exists a positive relationship between the number of common factors and group size.

This study also discovers that the sources of systematic risk are dissimilar due to the different periods in TSE. In full period the sources of risk are export of crude oil and interest rate proxy. In second sub periods money supply (M2), money supply (M1), consumer price index and GDP are sources of risk. So, the sources of systematic risks in TSE are dissimilar and not quantified. The important macroeconomic variables that could have affected stock returns changeover times. Therefore, it is hard to identify exactly which is the source of risk in TSE. Which macroeconomic variables are most important in Iran? These findings also suggest that different strategies are required to invest successfully in Iran because the risk factors changes over time.

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